

TABLE 2—EFFECTS OF DILUENTS ON EXTRACTION OF Pd^{II} WITH VERSATIC 10

Diluent	Extraction of Pd ^{II} %
Benzene	99.6
n-Hexane	97.8
Carbon tetrachloride	97.7
Chloroform	90.8
Xylene	91.3
Butanol	Emulsion
Toluene	72.6

(Table 2). Extraction behaviour of palladium(II) with Versatic 911 and SRS 100 has also been investigated. It was observed that the extraction of palladium(II) in case of SRS 100 was less than that of Versatic 911 (Table 3).

TABLE 3—COMPARATIVE EXTRACTION BEHAVIOUR OF Pd^{II} WITH DIFFERENT CARBOXYLIC ACID IN BENZENE DILUENT (1 : 6)

pH	Versatic 911 Extraction %	SRS 100 Extraction %
3.5	15.3	41
4.0	29.8	64.1
4.5	67.9	72.6
4.75	87.2	89.3
5.00	95.7	93.6
5.25	100	94.4
5.5	100	94.8
5.75	100	95.3

Extractive separation : Palladium(II) was separated from several binary mixtures using the recommended extraction conditions. Mg, Ca, Ba and Sr did not interfere. Interference of Co, Ni, Mn, Zn and Cd was removed by using selected stripping

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS ON EXTRACTION OF Pd^{II} WITH VERSATIC 10

(Palladium = 4.8 mg, Foreign Ions = 5 mg, pH = 5.75)

Ion	Pd extracted %	Selective stripping agent
Mg ^{II}	99.8	
Ca ^{II}	99.8	
Ba ^{II}	99.7	
Sr ^{II}	99.7	
Fe ^{III} *	100.2	
Co ^{II}	99.2	1 N H ₂ SO ₄
Ni ^{II}	99.6	1 N H ₂ SO ₄
Mn ^{II}	99.6	1 N HCl
Zn ^{II}	99.4	0.5 N HCl
Cd ^{II}	99.4	1 N HCl
Al ^{III} *	98.0	
Th ^{IV} *	99.0	

*NaF used as masking agent.

agent, and interference of Al, Fe and Th by using NaF as masking agent (Table 4). Most of the platinum metals however interfere.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Shell Co. Ltd. (London) for the gift samples of Versatic 10 and Versatic 911. Financial support from C.S.I.R., New Delhi to one of them (J. M.) is sincerely appreciated. The authors are grateful to Prof. A. K. De, Head, Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati for encouragement.

References

1. U. S. RAY and S. C. MODAK, *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, 1981, 16, 87.
2. U. S. RAY and S. C. MODAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 38.
3. A. W. ASHBROOK, *Miner. Sci. Eng.*, 1973, 5.
4. A. W. ASHBROOK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, 34, 1721.
5. R. PRIBIL, "Chelometry-basic Determinations", Chempol, Prague, 1961.
6. J. SHIBATA and S. NISHIMURA, *Nippon Kinzoku Gakkaigishi*, 1975, 39, 206, 767.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Indium(III) with 1-(2-Thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol

J. KRISHNAMA CHARYULU and M. C. ESHWAR*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay-400 076

Manuscript received 8 April 1986, revised 25 September 1986, accepted 13 November 1986

THIAZOLYLAZO dyes give¹ sensitive methods for spectrophotometric determination of various metal ions in polar or non-polar phase. The complex formed between indium(III) and 2-(4-methyl-2-thiazolylazo)-5-ethylamino-*p*-cresol² requires extraction into chloroform. Maximum colour development takes place after 15 min in the reaction with 4-(2-thiazolylazo)resorcinol^{3,4}, and many ions are also found to interfere. The reaction of indium(III) with 5-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid⁵ and 1-(2-thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid⁶ has resulted in useful methods for its determination in polar phase. Since 1-(2-thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol (TAN) has been found¹ to be a sensitive chromogenic reagent, the reaction between indium(III) and TAN has been studied.

Experimental

Apparatus employed were the same as described earlier⁷. Stock solution indium(III), prepared by dissolving of indium sulphate pentahydrate (Fluka) (3.308 g) in 1% sulphuric acid (250 ml), was standardised complexometrically. A 0.1% (w/v) solution of TAN (Fluka) was prepared in methanol. Buffer solution of pH 3.5 was prepared from 0.05 M solutions of acetic acid and sodium hydroxide (B.D.H.). All other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Procedure: To an aliquot of indium(III) solution containing $\leq 80 \mu\text{g}$ of indium(III), acetate buffer (5 ml) of pH 3.5 and 0.1% methanolic TAN (1 ml) were added. The complex was dissolved in 1,4-dioxan (5 ml), the solution diluted to 25 ml with distilled water and the absorbance measured at 575 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

On varying pH of the reaction mixture from 2.0 to 7.0, maximum absorbance was observed in the pH range 3.25–3.75. All studies were thus made at pH 3.5 and acetate buffer was most useful to maintain the pH. Since absorbance remained constant on addition of 1 to 8 ml buffer, 5 ml of acetate buffer of pH 3.5 was employed for all studies. When varying amounts (0.25–2.0 ml) of 0.1% TAN were added to a solution containing $< 50 \mu\text{g}$ of indium(III), the absorbance was found to be maximum in presence of ≥ 0.9 ml of reagent. Hence, 1 ml of reagent was used for all studies. The sparingly soluble complex was found to be soluble in dioxan and some other polar organic solvents. Since maximum absorbance was obtained in presence of 5–6 ml (20–24% v/v) of dioxan, 5 ml of dioxan was chosen for all further studies.

Since the In^{III} –TAN complex exhibited maximum absorbance at 575 nm and the reagent at 490 nm, all measurements were made at 575 nm. Both mole-ratio and Job's continuous variation methods established the metal–ligand ratio in the complex as 1 : 1. Formation constant ($\log K$) was found to be 3.83 by mole-ratio method⁸ and 3.24 by continuous variation method⁹. The complex adhered to Beer's law over the concentration range 0.1–3.2 μg of In^{III} per ml. Molar absorptivity, obtained from Beer's law plot, was $2.15 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell sensitivity 8.6 ng cm^{-2} . The instantaneously formed complex was stable for 2.5 h.

Interference of 53 ions was studied by setting the tolerance limit to cause $\pm 2\%$ error in determination of indium(III). Among the ions interfering at all levels, positive interference was caused by Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Sc^{III} and Ce^{III} , whereas Sb^{III} and EDTA caused negative interference. Tolerance limits for other ions are (in μg): nitrite, nitrate, Ba^{II} 10 000; chloride, bromide, Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} 8 000; iodide 6 000; urea 4 000; cyanide 3 000; ascorbate, succinate, thiourea, thiocyanate, Be^{II} , Al^{III} 2 000; Hg^{IIa} 1 250; $\text{NH}_4\text{OH.HCl}$ 1 000; Mn^{IIc} , Au^{IIIc} 750; Ag^{Ic} 600; Pt^{IVc} 450; Y^{III} , Tl^{IIIc} 300; tartrate, Rh^{IIIb} 250; citrate, N_2H_4 , H_2SO_4 , Th^{IV} , Mo^{VI} 200; Bi^{III} 150; malonate, Cd^{IIa} , Cr^{III} , La^{III} , Ge^{IV} , Se^{IV} 100; fluoride 50; oxalate, Fe^{IIc} , Co^{IIc} , Zn^{IIc} , Pd^{IIc} , Fe^{IIIc} , Ga^{III} , V^{IVc} 25. Some of the interfering ions were masked with ^aiodide, ^bthiourea, ^ccyanide and ^dthiocyanate.

Ten replicate determinations with 50 μg of indium(III) per 25 ml gave coefficient of variation and relative mean error as $\pm 0.2\%$ and $\pm 0.34\%$, respectively.

References

1. H. R. HOVIND, *Analyst*, 1975, **100**, 769.
2. E. M. NIKOLAEVA, *Tr. Perm. Med. In t.*, 1972, **108**, 67 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, **79**, 73205)
3. J. MINCZEWSKI, E. GRZEGRZOLKA and K. KASIURA, *Chem. Anal.*, 1968, **13**, 601.
4. M. LANGOVA, M. HNILICKOVA and L. SOMMER, *Talanta*, 1969, **16**, 681.
5. K. KASIURA and M. SZCZYGIELSKA, *Chem. Anal.*, 1971, **16**, 671.
6. A. I. BUSEV, T. N. ZHOLONDKOVSKAYA, L. S. KRYSINA and N. A. GOLUBKOVA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1972, **27**, 2165.
7. G. V. RATHAIAH and M. C. ESHWAR, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1985, **58**, 2447.
8. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4469.
9. A. K. MUKHERJI and A. K. DEY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **6**, 314.